

INVESTIGATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF A NIGERIAN AND A LIBERIAN BENTONITE FOR FOUNDRY APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

A Nigerian, and a Liberian Bentonite has been studied. The two Bentonite samples which were obtained from the natural geological source were critically studied. The study covered the physical, chemical, and the foundry properties of the two Bentonites. The sieve analysis of the sand used for the investigation of the foundry properties was also carried out. The result showed that the Liberian Bentonite is a sodium based Bentonite, with a Na₂O content of 1.91% with only traces of CaO. The Bentonite equally had a swelling index of 15, and green shear and compression strengths of 6.90KN/m² and 65.50KN/m². The Nigerian Bentonite is more or less a calcium based Bentonite with a CaO content of 2.83%, swelling index of 6.67, the green shear and compression strengths are less than those of the Liberian Bentonite. The two Bentonites however, have good foundry properties, which meets foundry standards.

KEYWORDS: Nigerian; Liberian; Bentonite; Foundry Application; Investigation.

INTRODUCTION

The West African sub-region is blessed with a lot of solid mineral deposit. Nigeria and Liberia are two countries found in the western part of Africa. These two countries have assorted types of mineral deposits ranging from metal ores, clays, to gemstones, diamonds and many others. Research had shown that most of the ores and minerals deposit from Liberia are of older geological age than those from Nigeria [Usman,1999]. This research has been confirmed with iron ores obtained from the two countries [Adiewere *et al*, 1996]. Foundry technology in Nigeria is mainly based on the sand casting technique which requires a lot of Bentonite as a binder for the silica sand for moulding mixture preparation [Okeke and Sadjere,1991]. Rich and quality Bentonites of the class called sodium Bentonite abound in Liberia. Nigeria is equally blessed with millions of metric tons of Bentonite deposits scattered in different regions of the country. These include Bentonite from Born in Sokoto, Ameki bende in Abia State, Barkin ladi in Plateau States of Nigeria and many others [RMRDC,1999]. Bentonite clays are special clays discovered first in France, Sweden (Montmorillonite or Smectite), and near Fort Benton in Wyoming (Bentonite) USA. They have several advantages over other clay types like Kaolinite and illite, and find wider application in the foundry than any of the other types [Nwajagu and Oji, 1991].

Industrial and non-metallic minerals are significant variables in the process of economic and industrial development of the Nation [Adekale,2003]. Bentonite belongs to the group of clays whose technical properties are controlled by the proportion of montmorillonite, a sub-group within the smectites. The annual National demand for Bentonite is about 100,000 tones in the oil sector alone and about 50,000 tones in the steel sector, this is expected to increase due to more petroleum exploration works, and application in other various industries [RMRDC, 1999, Ihom *et al*, 2006] in Nigeria.

One of the widely quoted and generally accepted definitions of Bentonite by geologists is that of Shannon [RMRDC,1999, Ihom and Anbua, 2006] which defines it as a rock composed essentially of a crystalline clay-like mineral formed by devitrification and the accompanying chemical alteration of glass igneous material, usually a tuff or volcanic ash. Bentonite defined strictly along this line has not been reported in Nigeria.

The product specification for foundry Bentonite is, the material should be in dry powder form, free from lumps, sand and other foreign materials. A minimum of the dry materials shall pass through the 200 mesh (U.S. Sieve) or 75 microns (I.S. Sieve). The moisture content should be 6-12%, pH value of between 8 and 10, calcium oxide content of 0.70% maximum; and liquid limit of 600 to 850 [Ojo, 1994].

The objectives of this work are to investigate the quality of these two Bentonites from Nigeria and Liberia. To let the world and industrialists know that this mineral is existing in these two countries and to let academicians and industrialists know the properties of the two Bentonites, and their suitability for foundry application.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The two Bentonite samples used for this work were obtained from Liberia and Nigeria. They were obtained from natural geological deposits and tested as such with no additives for activation.

Equipment

The equipment used were those of the National Metallurgical Development Centre, Jos, foundry laboratory. They include; laboratory ball mill, set of sieves, test tube, electronic digital balance, specific gravity bottle, universal strength testing machine, electric permimeter, shatter index device, compactability device, sand rammer, and speedy moisture tester.

Methods

The two Bentonites were obtained from their natural geological deposits in Liberia and Jos-Barkin ladi Nigeria. They were washed and dried to remove organic matter. The drying took place both in the sun and in the oven, where they were dried to a consistent weight at the temperature of 105°C using a laboratory ball mill the two samples were separately ground to -75 microns.

Table1: Physical properties of Liberian Bentonite and Nigerian Bentonite

S/N	Property	Liberian Bentonite	Nigerian bentonite
1.	Specific gravity	1.25	0.67
2.	Moisture content	6.8%	1.5%
3.	Swelling index	15.0	6.67
4.	Fineness	(75-150 µm) 60%	(75-150)75%
5.	Gel value	25cc	22cc
6.	Colour	Pale white	Dark yellow
7.	Liquid limit	850	110
8.	pH Value	9.0	4.0

Table2: Chemical Composition of the Liberian and Nigerian Bentonites

Composition	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	LOI
Liberian Bentonite	74.64	12.96	1.16	-	Traces	2.77	1.91	0.57	16.50
Nigerian Bentonite	69.00	13.33	2.09	0.22	2.83	3.38	1.93	0.01	12.15

Table3: Sieve Analysis of the River Benue Foundry Sand Used for the Foundry Properties Test

S/No	ISO Aperture Size (µm)	Sieve No	Weight Retained (g)	Percent Weight Retained	Cumulative Weight (g)	Product
1	1400	14	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.00
2	1000	18	0.70	0.70	1.10	9.80
3	710	25	2.20	2.20	3.30	39.60
4	500	35	5.30	5.30	8.60	132.50
5	355	45	10.50	10.50	19.10	367.50
6	250	60	27.20	27.20	46.30	1224.00
7	180	80	22.20	22.20	68.50	1332.00
8	125	120	19.30	19.30	87.80	1544.00
9	90	170	7.70	7.70	95.50	924.00
10	63	230	3.50	3.50	99.00	595.00
11	- 639(pan)	-230	1.00	1.00	100.00	230.00
						Σ6398.40

The following physical properties of the two sands were investigated: specific gravity, moisture content, liquid limit, swelling index, and fineness. The foundry properties of the two Bentonites were equally investigated. The foundry properties of the moulding mixtures prepared using these two Bentonites, which were investigated included: green shear strength, green compression strength, dry compression strength, dry shear strength, permeability, compactability, bulk density, shatter index, and the sieve analysis of the sand used. The moulding

mixtures for the tests were prepared using 5% water and 5% Bentonite. The 5% water and 5% Bentonite was chosen based on preliminary empirical results of tests carried out on the two Bentonites in the foundry of NMDC Jos.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

The results of the work are as displayed from Table 1-4. Table 1, shows the physical properties of Liberian and Nigerian Bentonites. The chemical composition of the two Bentonites is given in Table 2. Table 3 shows the sieve analysis of the River Benue foundry sand used for the foundry properties test. The foundry properties of the Bentonites are shown in Table 4.

Grain Fineness Number (GFN) = $6398.4/100 = 63.984$ AFS. The values in the table are used to calculate the GFN particularly the product sum and the cumulative weight sum.

Table4: Foundry Properties of the Two Bentonites

S/No	Property	Liberian Bentonite	Nigerian Bentonite
1	Moulding mixture content(%)	4.70	5.1
2	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	1.66	1.68
3	Green Shear Strength(KN/m ²)	6.90	6.21
4	Dry Shear Strength(KN/m ²)	458.52	256.49
5	Green Compression Strength(KN/m ²)	65.50	48.27
6	Dry Compression Strength (KN/m ²)	1206.63	1700
7	Weight for Standard Specimen (g)	163	165
8	Compactability (%)	54.17	51.67
9	Green Permeability(AFS perm unit)	350	270
10	Shatter Index %	42.95	13.94

DISCUSSION

Physical Properties of the Two Bentonites

Table 1, shows the physical properties of the Liberian and the Nigerian Bentonites. According to Forgham [1982] the main types of bonding clays used in foundries are the naturally occurring forms of the clay minerals montmorillonite, kaolinite and illite, and of these the most widely used are the sodium and calcium montmorillonites commonly known as Bentonites [Forgham, 1982].

After processing to a fine powder and controlled drying they may be supplied to the foundry as straight sodium or calcium Bentonite or alternatively the foundry properties of calcium Bentonite may be improved by synthetic conversion to the sodium form. Blends of any of these clays may be supplied to give the best composite properties for a particular application [Forgham,1982] the swelling index of the Liberian Bentonite is 15, while that of Nigerian Bentonite is 6.67.

It was observed that the Liberian Bentonite was highly plastic sticky and remained so even when excess water was added, it kept swelling. The Nigerian Bentonite lost its plasticity, stickiness and viscosity with excess water. It also ceased to swell as soon as it was over-ran with excess water. The moisture content of the Liberian Bentonite was 6.8%, which that of the Nigerian Bentonite was 6.0%. The Liberian Bentonite has a pH value of 9, while the Nigerian Bentonite has a pH value of 4. The Liberian Bentonite is Alkaline while the Nigerian Bentonite is acidic. The moisture content of the two Bentonites is within specified limit [Ihom and Olubajo, 2002]. According to Datta and Iyyadurai [1982] several tests are normally conducted to find the nature of the clay and thus its expected behaviour in a sand-clay –water system. Gelling index, cation exchange capacity base moisture content, specific gravity, electrical conductivity and methylene blue tests are some of the common tests while the more rigorous tests being X ray diffractographs, electron microscopy and differential thermal analysis. Some of these tests are quite reliable but not simple enough to be used as acceptance tests for accepting or rejecting a batch of materials.

The water absorptivity of a particular clay mineral is characterized by its structural configuration [Odom,1988]. A clay mineral which can absorb higher amount of moisture from the atmosphere is a better bonding clay [RMRDC, 1999, Odom, 1988]. This water absorption capacity of any clay mineral is dependent upon the relative humidity and the ambient temperature [Ihom, *et al*, 2006]. Gelling index and cation exchange capacity (CEC) values are normally used to assess the nature of the clay mineral and hence its bonding behaviour.

A clay mineral will have a higher specific gravity if it contains proportionately higher amount of nonclay minerals such as mica, quartz, feldspar, etc, in the bulk, and hence it will have a lower gelling index and also a lower C.E.C. Commenting on the differences in the amounts of exchangeable Na and Ca cations, Mizzi [1988] noted increasing evidence that the physical properties of montmorillonite clays have been shown to be dependent to a large extent on the exchangeable ions and soluble salts present in the clay [Mizzi,1988]

Chemical Composition of the Liberian and Nigerian Bentonites.

The chemical composition of the Liberian and Nigerian Bentonites is shown in Table 2. The result shows that the Nigerian Bentonite has high CaO content of 2.83% which is an indication that the clay is likely to be calcium base Bentonite. The chemical analysis falls within the range of composition given by RMRDC [1999] and Nwajagu [1994] for montmorillonite. Evidence furnished from literatures [RMRDC, 1999, Mizzi, 1988], however gave no hard and fast rules on using chemical analysis as positive identification of clay groups. Therefore the chemical composition of the Nigerian Bentonite is not sufficient in itself to confirm it as Bentonite. The physical properties in Table 1 however are similar to those of calcium Bentonites [RMRDC, 1999]. The Liberian Bentonite has traces of CaO and 1.91% Na₂O. This high value of Na₂O content indicates that it is a sodium Bentonite. The high swelling index of the clay and its other physical properties (Table 1) indicates that it is a sodium Bentonite. The chemical composition is also similar to that shown in references [RMRDC, 1999] and [Ojo, 1994] for sodium Bentonite.

Foundry Properties of the Two Bentonites

The foundry properties of the two Bentonites were investigated using a standard foundry sand the River Benue foundry sand (Tables 3). The sand is a 5-sieved sand with a grain fineness number (GFN) of 63.98 AFS. The sand agrees with the standard specification of a 5-sieved sand, and the 50 and above grain fineness number [Mizzi, 1988, Heine *et al*, 1967]. The same amount of water was used for the two clays. The moisture content test revealed 4.7% for Liberian Bentonite and 5.1% for Nigerian Bentonite, the mixing time was kept constant for the two clays (Table 4). The difference in the moisture content is likely as a result of the variation in water requirement of the two clays, sodium Bentonite requires more water to develop strength and to moisten than calcium Bentonite [Mizzi, 1988, Heine *et al*, 1967]. The bulk density of the Liberian Bentonite is 1.66 g/m³, which is slightly lower than the Nigerian Bentonite. The green shear and compression strength of the Liberian Bentonite are 6.90KN/m² and 65.50 KN/m², these values are higher than those of the Nigerian Bentonite which are 6.21KN/m² and 48.27KN/m². The shatter index of the Liberian Bentonite is 42.95%, while the Nigerian Bentonite has a shatter index of 13.94%. The Nigerian Bentonite however, has a higher dry compression strength of 1700KN/m² as against the Liberian Bentonite value of 1206.63KN/m², this difference is really hard to understand, given the high plasticity of the Liberian Bentonite it is expected that it would have a higher compression strength. This difference may be explained in terms of the high shrinkage and contraction, the Liberian Bentonite undergoes during drying giving rise to cracks, and several weak areas in the bonding between the clay and the sand. The degree of contraction is less during drying, in the case of the Nigerian Bentonite [Ihom, and Olubajo, 2002]. The two Bentonites have foundry properties that meets foundry specification particularly the green and dry strengths which are in both cases above 10KN/m² and 350KN/m² necessary for moulding and casting [Ojo, 1994, Brown, 1994].

The two Bentonites also have good green permeability which is above 100 AFS perm unit [Brown, 1994]. The compactability is high in the two clays and quite close, 54.17% for Liberian clay and 51.67% for Nigerian Bentonite. The properties are quite competitive, but for moulds to be used in the green condition the Liberian Bentonite will be better [Brown, 1994]. The Liberian clay has less organic matter and does not require beneficiation before pulverizing.

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained from this study it can be concluded that:-

1. The Liberian Bentonite is a sodium base Bentonite, while the Nigerian Bentonite is a calcium base Bentonite.
2. The Liberian Bentonite swells more than the Nigerian Bentonite, the Nigerian Bentonite requires activation for it to swell like the Liberian Bentonite.
3. The two Bentonites have good foundry properties as shown by the test results, the Liberian Bentonite is however better in most of the properties.
4. The results have shown that the two Bentonites can be used by the foundry for sand casting moulding mixture preparation.

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